

Nascent Stage of the Hyper loop Transportation Industry –A Huge Socio- Economic Opportunity

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Abstract: The hyper loop is thought to be the fastest land-based mode of transportation, in which small cars are sent through a tube structure borne by pillars at a speed that is purportedly faster than the average aircraft speed. The moving pod travelling inside the vacuum tube and the surface of the tube barely interact, which allows for this extremely high speed. In other terms, the tube contains nearly no air, meaning that there is no air resistance. Electromagnets installed around the tube and the pod, also known as the “passenger capsule,” hangs it inside. There are no actual hyper loop projects in existence today because this idea is so innovative and technically distinct. In July 2019, the Maharashtra government chose DP World Hyper Loop Technologies as the project's proponent. Subsequently, the project received public infrastructure status, allowing it to more easily access funding and concessions. The Project reportedly received a significant investment of Rs. 70,000cr. The Pune Metropolitan Regional Development Authority (PMRDA) was designated by the Maharashtra government as an implementing agency, and the organisation planned to issue bids in 2019 due to the Covid -19 epidemic. The main concerns are the current situation and the extent of its technical and financial viability. Challenges and it provides first-hand knowledge to concerned stakeholders. The Paper's main objective is to provide stakeholders a complete analysis of the importance of project development, funding, construction issues and challenges.

Key Words: Infrastructure, Hyper loop, PMRDA, Virgin HO, funding and PPP

INTRODUCTION

As of July 2018, there were roughly 10 Indian cities with a functioning intra-city rail network spanning nearly 450 km, and eleven more such projects are in the works through 2024. However, intercity transportation is falling behind in adopting the latest technologies that would enable seamless travel between various regions of the nation. Although flying is a possibility, the expenses are high, and the industry is more concerned with meeting travellers' basic needs than it is with creating innovative technologies. This expansion is being fuelled by India's explosive urban population growth. Another aspect of this story is the connectivity within cities, which is supported by new rail and road corridors that offer a regular solution to the issue at hand. Here, we have a hyper loop that can link cities, offer next-generation logistics, reduce costs, and leave a smaller carbon footprint. By 2024, India, which has 1.37 billion people, will surpass China as the world's most populous nation. The issues that our population will face in the future are not adequately anticipated by all. The impact on the resources caused by an increase in population exacerbates existing issues. Low per capita income, unemployment, illiteracy, corruption, and crime are only a few consequences of an expanding population. Given that 40% of the country's population is expected to live in urban areas by 2030, rural to urban migration is one of India's main concerns going forward. India is no exception, as urbanisation will account for nearly 70% of the population by 2050.

The tremendous population growth in India's metropolitan areas will need the construction of 500 new cities. Indian towns should develop nearby areas so that the city structure can be planned in advance and proper transportation and infrastructure are included in the plan. Indian cities are not well-equipped to handle the problems and they should plan

to fulfil the requirements of a growing population. Congestion on the roads is one such issue. Indian passengers have become accustomed to dealing with this issue throughout their lives, and the commute is now more than just inconvenient. Mumbai has 2,000 km of roads (as opposed to 28,000 km in Delhi), and the density of private cars there increased by 18% in just the last two years. As a result, Mumbai's traffic flow is close to 500 cars per km of road, and the maximum City's car-congestion is nearly five times higher than Delhi's 100 or more cars. Overall, the number of private cars in Mumbai is less than one-third that in the national capital. Pune comes ranked second in terms of vehicle congestion, with roughly 360 automobiles per kilometre.

A person who works for a living won't have to commute as far from home thanks to the Hyper Loop, which also makes travel hassle-free, and will be able to get at work on time thanks to a practical, economical, and environmentally friendly form of transportation. The transportation industry is sorely suffering from severe traffic congestion and lack of trip comfort, yet the hyper loop as a new method of transportation has much to offer. According to reports, it will provide us the speed of aeroplanes on land with improved safety and productive repetitive jobs that can be automated to provide a one-stop solution to speed up transportation and set new records. It addresses a variety of problems that many nations who want to advance in the field of contemporary transportation are currently facing.

HYPER LOOP INDUSTRY SCENARIO

In the initial stage, Virgin Hyperloop One, DP World, and Summa Group would combine their efforts to build the demonstration track. On April 4, 2017, Elon Musk, a well-known figure in the technology sector, published a white paper titled "Hyper Loop Alpha" in which he provided a general description of a new mode of transportation that could be regarded as the fifth mode of transportation. He urged everyone to work toward making this a reality. 2019 (Elon Musk). This sparked widespread curiosity and created a brand-new area of study (Rytham, A.2019). The Mumbai-Pune corridor has been identified by the firm as one of the most practicable routes since it offers two sister towns within 115 kilometres of one another and a significant rider ship of 150 million passenger trips annually. The technological business has raised \$295 million since its founding (as of the December 2017 report) and has enough money to do research on the Hyper loop technology in order to offer a one-stop solution. The Hyper Loop Technology Market is anticipated to grow at a CAGR of 47.20 percent between 2022 and 2026, from a value of USD 1.35 billion in 2022 to USD 6.34 billion in 2026. The pod travels more quickly thanks to hyper loop's usage of vacuum technology. Lack of knowledge about the technology, rules set by the government, and numerous safety and security concerns are the main inhibitors for the market for Hyper loop technology.

Numerous businesses are developing different components of this new mode of transportation. Aecom, Transpod Inc., MIT Hyperloop, Badger loop, VicHyper, Delft Hyper loop, Open Loop, BITS Hyper loop, AZLoop, UW Hyper loop, and WARR Hyper loop are a few of the major players in the Hyperloop market. Hyperloop One, SpaceX, Dgw Hyper loop, Hyperloop Transportation Technologies, BITS Hyper loop, AZLoop, UW Hyper loop, and WARR Hyper loop are other notable names These businesses are investigating various facets of the new mode. This necessitates the creation of an entirely new procedure. The rise in demand for speedier modes of transportation is a major driver of the global market for Hyper Loop technology. The market is growing due to the transportation technology's low cost in comparison to other means of transportation like land, water, air, and rail, as well as its energy efficiency and environmental friendliness. The likelihood of technological problems and a lack of power, however, serve as significant

commercial restrictions. It is projected that the reduction in traffic congestion will present profitable prospects for the market's manufacturers.

Table 1 Comparison between Conventional Modes of Travel and the Hyper Loop

Hyper loop	Conventional Modes
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The entire system would be self-powering and run on miles of track-mounted solar panels providing a sustainable power source that might considerably lower operating costs in the future. • Hyper loop pods travel at speeds of roughly 1100 kmph, which is two to three times faster than the 400 kmph top speed of the highest high-speed rail. • This form of transportation is direct and on-demand; it departs when passengers are ready to do so, similar to the just-in-time principle and improving queue management. • Hyper loop has also concentrated on the noise pollution produced by physical contact-based transportation systems. Noise is projected to be another significant feature working in the system's favour based on the physics of non-contact motion through a steel tube. • The safety elements that Hyper Loop offers demonstrate the movement toward Vision Zero in the transportation sector. Since many people are reportedly killed in conventional train and road accidents, this objective is to achieve 100% safety. • Because it is a fully contained system, the sector has the capacity to model and regulate the entire environment as a new method of transportation. Hyper loop is thought to be safer since it has steel casings that shield the system from interruption. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Because of poor speeds and high operating expenses, the majority of government-owned railroad firms are not profitable, which indicates that railroads are slowly losing their usefulness and will soon need to be replaced. • Rail transportation always adheres to a specific daily schedule with numerous stops along the way because it travels such great distances. • A large amount of electrical power is needed for the High-Speed Rail's traction, which will likely increase operating costs unless a power-saving system is built-in. • Physical contact causes wear and tear in the vehicle and the roadway it travels on, which has always been the basis for determining the tyre pressures for road transportation or the flaws emerging in rail wheels like thermal cracking or shelling would not be needed and eventually become superfluous. • The decision-making process and project implementation in the rail and bus transportation industries are heavily influenced by the bureaucratic system. • Rail projects are extremely time-consuming and costly.

Source: Compiled by Author

MUMBAI-PUNE HYPER LOOP CASE STUDY

In order to enter the new era of an integrated technology including the hyper loop cum pod transportation, the government of Maharashtra and Virgin Hyper Loop One, a transport innovations firm with US headquarters, entered into an agreement in February 2018. It is thought that the business has the necessary skills to complement the current transportation infrastructure and lighten the load on frequent travellers in the area. A letter of intent (LoI) and a memorandum of understanding (MoU) have reportedly been signed by the Maharashtra government and the company, respectively, to begin a feasibility study for the development of the Hyper Loop project in the Mumbai-Pune region using a public-private partnership (PPP) model (ENS, 2019). According to the recently passed Maharashtra Infrastructure Policy Act, the Hyper Loop has received approval (2018). The project's public infrastructure status will contribute to increased process efficiency and time savings. Virgin Hyper loop one intended to build a test route over a distance of 15 km from Balewadi to Gahunje in 2019 after submitting the feasibility report and the Detailed Project Report (DPR) (Pandey,P.2019). Once the test track is deemed successful, project planning will be completed. For the development of the project, the "Swiss Challenge Method" (SCM) of contract is suggested. As a result, MIDEA classified the project as a public infrastructure project. The Original Project Proponent (OPP) of the DP world-Virgin Hyper Loop consortium will shortly receive the infrastructure certificate and be required to create a DPR that can be contested by other bidders under the SCM method of contracting (Deshpande, A., 2019). And after the DPR is released, any bidder may offer comments for enhancing the first proposal. In other words, the OPP status and financial responsibility for the project will be granted to the bidder who presents the best proposal. The land needed to complete the initial pilot project, which will include a test track and the main track in the future, will be provided by the State Government. However, since the track route for the hyper loop is intended to run alongside the Mumbai-Pune Existing Expressway, no land acquisition is necessary.

SALIENT FEATURES OF HYPER LOOP TECHNOLOGY

- The Hyper loop is expected to carry over 30,000 passengers every day in circular trips at a design speed of over 1000 kph.
- The pod is reportedly 2.23 m wide, has a stainless steel body, longitudinal seats, and can accommodate 28 passengers in one pod unit with air conditioning (Fig.1).
- With a headway of 30 seconds, the number of pods would move sequentially along two parallel tubes for incoming and leaving air.
- Three different alignment types—at-grade, elevated, and underground—can be accommodated by the system with ease. The raised alignment is seen in Fig.3
- DP World, Caspian VC Partners, Virgin Group, Sherpa Capital, Abu Dhabi Capital Group, SNCF, GE Ventures, Formation 8, 137 Ventures, and WTI are a few of the major investors for the projects.
- The Maharashtra government and Hyperloop One have suggested a public-private partnership as the building model.
- PMRDA, MMRDA, Virgin Hyperloop One, and other consultancy firms would form an SPV.
- The entire term of operations and maintenance can be viewed as 50 years, during which time new routes can be added.

HYPER LOOP ISSUES

Due to the enormous number of daily commuters and the overwhelming population of the two cities, the proposed Hyper Loop connecting Pune and Mumbai appears possible; however, there are many issues that need to be taken into account because the system's implementation is complicated and expensive. There is a huge risk involved in

building and running this new system because the project in India will be one of the first of its kind in the world. Additionally, it is challenging to determine the costs involved. Many economists scoff at Musk's \$7.5 billion price estimates in his white paper.

By 2025, the proposed line between Pune and Mumbai is expected to be finished. The PMRDA started the land acquisition process, however delays are unavoidable because, as is typical in Indian projects, land acquisition is the primary factor contributing to project delays. The government cannot simply ignore steep and low terrain and seize land at low market value, as they did in the case of the existing Mumbai-Pune expressway, making land acquisition more difficult.

The project's total cost is difficult to predict because it will increase as it is delayed more. Additionally, a hyper loop needs a track without any sharp turns or curves because a vessel or pod travelling at the speed of sound will feel uncomfortable if its direction changes. Elon Musk conducted a feasibility study for the Hyper Loop in the United States, where there are many miles of straight highways and stringent right-of-way laws. Elon suggested using these laws to justify the system's low cost by avoiding the need for the government to purchase new land.

These two cities are already well connected with a number of trains, an expressway, and an outdated highway, which provides passengers with last-mile connectivity via a number of local train stations and a road network. Existing transportation options with more capacity, including bullet trains and maglev, can also be taken into consideration. The capacity of each pod, which is estimated to hold 800 passengers per hour, is the next potential area of concern given the high-profile commuter demand between Mumbai and Pune, where it is estimated that there are approximately 20,000,000 total passenger trips per day.

One of the main issues with the Hyper Loop system is the need for a large number of vacuum pumps, which can be deployed in a variety of configurations but still require high energy consumption, resulting in high operational costs. The entire tube would need to be shut down if a leak were to develop. Due to the fact that pods can only depart the tube at a station, a higher level of security is required. There aren't many resources available, thus passengers are unable to get up from their seats during the trip or seek medical attention if necessary. The idea is to cover the tubes with solar panels to make the project completely energy-free, but this will just increase the project's construction costs.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

The hyper loop is a futuristic mode of transportation that is positioned as the future of mass transit. Reduced friction with the air or the ground, which limits the speed of traditional trains, is the fundamental goal of the hyperloop. The system consists of four major parts, namely: a long tube, ground-level pillars, solar panels, and pods. On pillars, the tube is raised above the surface. It has solar panels installed at various points along the bridge to produce electricity to power the running pods. The elevated path is divided into different parts as well to absorb motions brought on by any earthquakes. There are currently no hyper loop initiatives being carried out anywhere in the globe, as far as the technology is concerned. But the expert teams are working toward deploying one between Mumbai and Pune in India and one between Los Angeles and San Francisco in the US (Musk, E,2019). Economically speaking, the project is anticipated to cut the time it takes to travel from Mumbai to Pune to just 30 minutes at a speed of roughly 500 kmph. According to the project's website, 26 million people in both cities will have better connectivity, and 150 million people are anticipated to use the service yearly. Two stages—namely viz.

(i). A test track on the Mumbai-Pune alignment's 11.4 kilometre stretch is seen in Figs. 1 and 2. This phase, which is considered a pilot project, is expected to cost Rs. 5000 crore.

(ii). The second phase completes the project to link Kurla in Mumbai with Wakad in Pune. The Covid Pandemic significantly delayed the PMRDA's scheduled mid-August 2019 launch of bidding for the project, which is expected to cost Rs. 70,000.00 cr and involve foreign direct investment.

Fig. 1 Proposed route between Pune and Mumbai

Fig. 2 Hyper loop capsule in tube cutaway with attached solar arrays

Fig. 3 Elevation of Hyper loop Structure

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